

COMPARISON OF SUBMUCOSAL RESECTION (SMR) AND CAUTERIZATION IN TREATMENT OF TURBINATE HYPERTROPHY

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Abstract

Objective: To compare submucosal resection and bipolar cauterization as surgical intervention for inferior turbinate hypertrophy of the nose. To analyze post-operative complications of SMR and Mucosal cauterization. To assess post-surgical outcome of both techniques for nasal obstruction caused by ITH.

Study design: Prospective quasi-experimental comparative study

Methodology: The study included 100 surgical cases admitted through OPD from August, 2023 to June, 2024 at Combined Military Hospital, Kharian Cantt, Departments of Otorhinolaryngology. Patient from both genders, age between 20 to 35 years. These patients had no other comorbidities. The disease patterns of all candidates were different. Post operative complications and relief in nasal obstruction based on VAS were analyzed on follow up at 1 week, 1 month and 3 months for optimal results.

Results: A total of 100 patients underwent nasal surgery, 50 received **Submucosal Resection (Group1)** and 50 underwent **cauterization (Group2)**. In Group1 patients, postoperative **reactionary hemorrhage** occurred in 14 (28%) cases. In Group2, hemorrhage was noted in 4 (8%) cases, mostly in vasomotor rhinitis (1/8; 12.5%). **Facial pain at 1 month** was observed in 10 (20%) of SMR patients, whereas **cauterization** showed a higher rate of postoperative pain, with 14 (28%) patients affected. **Crusting at 1 month** was relatively uncommon, seen in only 2 (4%) SMR cases and 8 (16%) cauterization cases. Cauterization, therefore, showed a higher crusting tendency, particularly in males with allergic rhinitis (4/12; 33%). **Nasal synechiae at 2 months** were recorded in only 2 (4%) cases in the cauterization group and none in the SMR group.

Conclusion: It was found that overall surgical intervention was helpful in long term management of inferior turbinate hypertrophy in patients generally.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most vital organs of the human body is our nose. It has a pivotal role in humidifying, warming and filtration of the air we inspire. A most common presenting complaint from patients in ENT is having a stuffy or blocked nose.¹ Some patients also mention they witness a swollen nasal mass which can be unilateral or bilateral on self-examination. There are some physiological and physical factors that cause turbinate enlargement also known as hypertrophy.² The nasal cycle consisting of alternate enlargement and contraction of the inferior turbinates takes place multiple times in a day. Most individuals won't notice these changes but those who have anatomical anomalies such as septal deviations, a constrictive bony pyramid, a small nasal aperture or a limited nasal cavity may notice them clearly.³

Mostly affected turbinate in nasal cavity is the inferior turbinate and due to its anatomical distribution, enlargement can cause a partial to complete nasal obstruction symptoms. Size of the IT normally is 50-60mm long and 3.5mm wide.³ Airflow through nose is laminar. Velocity of the flow increases as it passes the valve of nose, then the flow becomes turbulent. This ensures prolonged contact of air with the internal structures of the nose and nasal mucosa. Pollens and antigens in the air trigger the innate immunity. IgA and IgE present on the mucosal surface. The clinician can have various objective measures of nasal function, rhinomanometry and acoustic rhinometry.⁴ The problem is that these objective measures of nasal function do not always correlate with the patient's own assessment of nasal sensations such as the sensation of nasal airflow. Objective test like rhinomanometry, acoustic rhinometry and peak nasal flow target the resistance influenced by nasal valve region.⁴ On the other hand the symptoms of nasal obstruction may be influenced by other areas of the nose along with the nasal valve area thus, subjective scores for nasal symptoms can provide the main outcome criteria for study and clinical trials on new treatments for diseases causing nasal obstructions.⁵

Nowadays the general terminology used for nasal inflammatory diseases is Rhinosinusitis. This includes inflammation of nasal mucosal and disease of the paranasal sinuses. The term was coined considering the fact that untreated rhinitis is a leading cause of sinusitis and sinusitis in general is accompanied by symptoms of rhinitis and nasal flow obstruction.⁶ Host factors for this disorder include congenital/genetics, allergen exposure, any systemic disease, infections and it can also be iatrogenic in nature.

Inferior turbinate surgery was 1st described by Jones in 1890s. then again Holmes stated the stages of turbinate hypertrophy and had a surgical experience of over 1500 surgeries.⁷ Turbinate excision procedures can be complete, partial or subtotal. Total turbinectomy is discouraged due to prolonged crusting of nasal mucosa and it may cause empty nose syndrome. Partial or subtotal turbinoplasty also known as turbinate resection. At times turbinate bone is removed in the surgery while the mucosa is preserved. Other methods included are submucosal diathermy, submucosal resection, radiofrequency ablation, cryotherapy, laser-assisted ablation, ultrasonic reduction and mucosal cauterization.⁸

The technique of submucosal resection and mucosal electric cauterization was described in a 1990.⁹ The enlargement of the inferior turbinates, obstructing the nasal passages, is a hallmark of rhinitis. Most of the time, the middle turbinates do not get in the way of airflow unless there is a deformity in the nose or an ethmoidal cell that has grown into the turbinate. Under certain conditions like allergic, vasomotor and other iatrogenic rhinopathies, the mucus membrane and soft tissue of the inferior turbinates change permanently and get thicker, which can make it hard to breathe. So, the growth of the inferior turbinates is mostly caused by the mucosa getting hypertrophied and only at times by the bone is involved. Patients who have had nasal obstructions in the past because of inferior turbinate hypertrophy and whose symptoms aren't responding to medication need surgery to ease their symptoms and provide a permanent relief.¹⁰ The purpose of these surgeries is to

maintain the physiological function of nasal cavity while reducing the anatomical mass of inferior turbinates.

Methodology:

A total of 100 patients from January 2023 to June 2024, were included in this **prospective, quasi-experimental, comparative study** from CMH Kharian, ENT department (Institutional Review Board CMH, Kharian no. A/24/30 approved on 14th Dec, 2022). Sampling technique was **non-probability convenience** sampling. The sample size for this study was calculated using OpenEpi, an open-source epidemiologic tool consistent with WHO guidance. With a **95% confidence interval** and **5% margin of error** and applying finite population correction due to a limited target population, the required sample size was calculated as 100. Previous quasi-experimental studies conducted in similar contexts used sample size of 90 participants¹³. Therefore, a sample size of 100 was deemed sufficient to ensure comparability and improve statistical precision. Group differences for **categorical data were analyzed using the Chi-square test**. Candidates were allotted in two groups, 50 in each named as **Group 1** and **Group 2**.

- Group 1 = operated using **Submucosal Resection technique** (n=50)
- Group 2 = turbinoplasty via **Cauterization** (n=50)

Patients selected from outpatient center (OPD) with a history of nasal obstruction or stuffiness not cured by medical treatment for prolonged periods and advised elective surgical intervention. Written informed consent and pre-anesthesia assessment was done. All surgeries in **Group 1** were performed by the same consultant, and all surgeries in **Group 2** were performed by another consultant, both having more than **five years of post-**

graduate surgical experience.

Inclusion criteria:

Those patients who are not under 20 years and older than 35 years. They did not have high blood pressure or any other comorbidity that may

cause excessive bleeding and delayed healing are included in the study. Participants had signed a written consent form and were well aware of their participation in this research study. These patients were diagnosed with chronic hypertrophic rhinitis, allergic rhinitis, vasomotor rhinitis and had inferior turbinate hypertrophy.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients under 20 years old, over 35 years old, with high blood pressure or diabetes, or who had other comorbidities were not included in the study. Patients who had gross DNS requiring Septoplasty procedure were also not included. Patients who were unable to follow-up and were not willing to participate in the research study were not included. Exclusion was done on **clinical examination and laboratory investigations.**

Procedure:

All the patients were informed about the procedure and its effectiveness. A written and informed consent was taken. Candidates were advised radiological investigations i.e., **proper computerized tomography of complete paranasal sinuses in Axial and Coronal views.**^{2,3,11,12} Patients were admitted a day before surgery. Both techniques were performed under **general anesthesia** using standard surgical procedures. **Group 1 underwent SMR** for turbinate hypertrophy while **Group 2 had turbinoplasty by Mucosal Cauterization**. The anesthesia protocol was identical in both groups. Similar duration of hospital stay and discharge plan along with similar post-operative medication was ensure.¹³ Regular follow ups 1st after 1 week then every month for next 6 months.

Data Analysis:

Data were analyzed using **SPSS version 29.0**. **Mean ± SD** was calculated for continuous variables, and **frequencies (%)** for categorical variables. The **Chi-square test** was used for comparison, with a **p-value < 0.05** considered statistically significant.

Surgery Type	Gender	Disease Pattern	Reactionary Hemorrhage (Yes, %)	Facial Pain (Yes, %)	Crusting (Yes, %)	Nasal Synechiae (Yes, %)
SMR	Male	Allergic Rhinitis	7 (39%)	0 (0%)	1 (6%)	0 (0%)
	Male	Vasomotor Rhinitis	0 (0%)	1 (8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
	Male	Chronic Hypertrophic Rhinitis	1 (14%)	2 (29%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Allergic Rhinitis	1 (25%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Vasomotor Rhinitis	4 (67%)	0 (0%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Chronic Hypertrophic Rhinitis	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Cauterization	Male	Allergic Rhinitis	1 (8%)	2 (17%)	4 (33%)	2 (17%)
	Male	Vasomotor Rhinitis	0 (0%)	5 (42%)	1 (8%)	0 (0%)
	Male	Chronic Hypertrophic Rhinitis	0 (0%)	4 (44%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Allergic Rhinitis	1 (14%)	3 (43%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Vasomotor Rhinitis	1 (13%)	0 (0%)	2 (25%)	0 (0%)
	Female	Chronic Hypertrophic Rhinitis	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Results:

A total of 100 patients underwent nasal surgery, 50 received **Submucosal Resection (SMR)** and 50 underwent **cauterization**. Among SMR patients, postoperative **reactionary hemorrhage** occurred in 14 (28%) cases, predominantly among males with allergic rhinitis (7/18; 38.9%). In contrast, in the cauterization group, hemorrhage was less common, noted in 4 (8%) cases, mostly in females with vasomotor rhinitis (1/8; 12.5%).

Facial pain at 1 month was observed in 10 (20%) of SMR patients, mostly in chronic hypertrophic rhinitis (3/10; 30%), whereas **cauterization** showed a higher rate of postoperative pain, with 14 (28%) patients affected, predominantly among

males with vasomotor and chronic hypertrophic rhinitis.

Crusting at 1 month was relatively uncommon, seen in only 2 (4%) SMR cases and 8 (16%) cauterization cases. Cauterization, therefore, showed a higher crusting tendency, particularly in males with allergic rhinitis (4/12; 33%).

Nasal synechiae at 2 months were rare, recorded in only 2 (4%) cases in the cauterization group and none in the SMR group. Overall, SMR demonstrated fewer long-term complications, while cauterization had a higher rate of transient postoperative crusting and facial discomfort.

At three months postoperatively, SMR showed a superior improvement, with 46 out of 50 patients (92%) reporting no to mild obstruction (VAS 0–3) and only 4 (8%) having moderate residual obstruction. In contrast, the cauterization group had a slightly lower improvement rate, with 38 (76%) showing no to mild obstruction and 12 (24%) reporting moderate obstruction. No patient in either group reported severe postoperative obstruction. The overall postoperative improvement rate (VAS ≤3) for all patients combined was 84%, with SMR yielding better symptom relief compared to cauterization (92% vs 76%). This suggests that submucosal resection was more effective in improving nasal airflow and reducing subjective nasal blockage over a 3 month follow up.

		Preoperative Nasal Obstruction VAS			Improvement Postoperative	Nasal VAS	VAS 3months
		no obstruction to mild 1-3 Count	moderate obstruction 4-7 Count	severe obstruction 8-10 Count	no to mild obstruction (0 - 3) Count	moderate obstruction (4 - 7) Count	severe obstruction (8 - 10) Count
Surge	Group 1	0	22	28	46	4	0
Group	Group 2	0	24	26	38	12	0

Statistical Analysis
Crosstabs:

- Surgery Groups: Preoperative Nasal Obstruction VAS Crosstabulation

		moderate obstruction 4-7	severe obstruction 8-	Total
Surgery_Group	SMR	22	28	50
p	Cauterization	24	26	50
Total		46	54	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.161 ^a	1	.688		
Continuity Correction ^b	.040	1	.841		
Likelihood Ratio	.161	1	.688		
Fisher's Exact Test				.841	.421
Linear-by-Linear Association	.159	1	.690		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 23.00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Before surgery, the severity of nasal obstruction was similar between the two groups. In the SMR group, 44% had moderate and 56% had severe obstruction, while in the Cauterization group, 48% had moderate and 52% had severe obstruction. The difference between the two groups was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 0.161$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.688$).

- **Surgery Groups and Improvement Nasal VAS at 3months Postoperative**

		Improvement Nasal VAS 3months Postoperative		
		no obstruction (0 - 3)	mild to moderate obstruction (4 - 7)	Total
Surgery_Group	SMR	46	4	50
p	Cauterization	38	12	50
Total		84	16	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.762 ^a	1	.029		
Continuity Correction ^b	3.646	1	.056		
Likelihood Ratio	4.949	1	.026		
Fisher's Exact Test				.054	.027
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.714	1	.030		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

There was a significant difference in postoperative nasal obstruction improvement between the two procedures. Patients who underwent Submucosal Resection (SMR) showed better outcomes (**92% with no-to-mild obstruction**) compared to Cauterization (**76%**). The association was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 4.76$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.029$).

- **Surgery Groups and Reactionary Hemorrhage at 1week**

		Reactionary hemorrhage 1week		Total
		yes	no	
Surgery_Group	SMR	14	36	50
p	Cauterization	3	47	50
Total		17	83	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.575 ^a	1	.003		
Continuity Correction ^b	7.087	1	.008		
Likelihood Ratio	9.185	1	.002		
Fisher's Exact Test				.006	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.490	1	.004		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Reactionary hemorrhage within one week was significantly more common in the SMR group (28%) compared to the Cauterization group (6%). The difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 8.58$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.003$).

- Surgery Groups and Facial pain at 1month

		Facial_pain_1month		Total
		yes	no	
Surgery_Group	SMR	5	45	50
	Cauterization	14	36	50
Total		19	81	100

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Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.263 ^a	1	.022		
Continuity Correction ^b	4.159	1	.041		
Likelihood Ratio	5.441	1	.020		
Fisher's Exact Test				.040	.020
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.211	1	.022		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

At one month post-surgery, facial pain was reported more frequently in the Cauterization group (28%) than in the SMR group (10%). This difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 5.26$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.022$).

- Surgery Groups and Crusting at 1month

		Crusting at 1month		Total
		yes	no	
Surgery_Group	SMR	2	48	50
	Cauterization	8	42	50
Total		10	90	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.000 ^a	1	.046		
Continuity Correction ^b	2.778	1	.096		
Likelihood Ratio	4.255	1	.039		
Fisher's Exact Test				.092	.046
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.960	1	.047		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Crusting at one month occurred more often after Cauterization (16%) than SMR (4%). The association reached statistical significance ($\chi^2 = 4.00$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.046$).

- **Surgery Groups and Nasal Synechia at 2months**

		Nasal Synechia at 2months		Total
		yes	no	
Surgery_Group	SMR	0	50	50
	Cauterization	2	48	50
Total		2	98	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.041 ^a	1	.153		
Continuity Correction ^b	.510	1	.475		
Likelihood Ratio	2.813	1	.093		
Fisher's Exact Test				.495	.247
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.020	1	.155		
N of Valid Cases	100				

a. 2 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Nasal synechia developed in **2 patients (4%)** following Cauterization, while none occurred after SMR. The difference was **not statistically significant** ($\chi^2 = 2.04$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.153$). Because 50% of expected counts were <5 , the **Fisher's Exact Test** is more reliable here ($p = 0.495$), confirming **no significant association**.

Discussion

Chronic nasal obstruction affects quality of life.¹⁴ Research indicates that partial inferior turbinectomy can be just as effective as total inferior turbinectomy for relieving nasal obstruction, with reported success rates of 70–80%. Nevertheless, the procedure should be performed carefully to avoid compromising the nose's anatomical structures and physiological functions.

According to a survey of the available literature, surgeons from all over the globe have been using a variety of procedures to shrink the size of inferior turbinates¹⁵. Kassem k. et al has mentioned radiofrequency ablation and coblation techniques which further broaden the horizon for surgical management.¹⁵

Mucosal electrocautery was observed to be less invasive, less expensive, and easily repeatable, consistent with the findings of Mahajan et al., (2019)⁴. Patients experienced improvement in nasal airflow; however, some reported transient burning sensations, unpleasant smell, mucociliary disruption, crusting, and mild bleeding. These complications are attributable to thermal injury to the mucosa, which may compromise ciliary function and increase the risk of adhesions.

According to Bastawy (2023)¹⁵, compared to mucosal electrocautery, submucosal resection improves the nasal airway more effectively, and it may be performed under either local or general anesthesia. The mucociliary process continues unabated. Because there is no exposed raw surface, adhesions are less likely formed. The downsides, however, include the fact that it requires technical expertise, and, in rare cases, may lead to significant bleeding as a result of secondary infections.^{16,17} Bone devitalization, sequestration, and eventual shedding of the inferior turbinate may occur in as little as two to

three months, causing crusting and blood-stained discharge.¹⁸

If a sinus surgery is required in a patient, the superior lateral surface of the inferior turbinate can be utilized as a landmark to find the thin bony lateral wall that divides the maxillary sinus from the middle meatus. Al-Baldawi et al. stated in his research that respiration causes physiologic vascular alterations, one of which is the turbinates' mucosal enlargement. Allergic reactions, infections, and hyperreactivity may amplify these alterations.¹⁹

In recent years, minimally invasive techniques such as endoscopic partial turbinectomy and microdebrider-assisted turbinoplasty have gained considerable attention. These approaches offer the promise of reduced postoperative complications, faster recovery, and improved patient comfort. Nevertheless, there remains a need for further research to establish their long-term efficacy, cost-effectiveness, and optimal patient selection, which could ultimately lead to better outcomes and a higher quality of care.

Conclusion

Submucosal resection was considered a better surgical technique and outperformed mucosal electrocautery, according to the findings of this study. After the surgery Submucosal Resection technique produced patient friendly results. Less post operative complications and improved nasal obstruction symptoms as compared to Mucosal electrocautery (cauterization) was seen. Better wound healing was observed and patients were able to return to daily routine activities earlier with submucosal resection as compared to Cauterization.

Conflict of interest: None

Study limitation:

- Variability in the methods used to assess symptom improvement, nasal airflow, and quality of life makes it difficult to directly compare results across studies.
- Study included 100 patients, this sample may still be relatively small to detect less common complications.
- The surgeries were performed by only two surgeons, which may introduce variability.

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